

Hexon

A171/Beijing/12/2021
CR8593/Beijing/12/2012
CR8716/Beijing/03/2013
CR8816/Beijing/05/2013
CR9662/Beijing/05/2014
F127/Beijing/06/2014
F1797/Beijing/07/2018
F1909/Beijing/07/2019
F2096/Beijing/12/2019
F2230/Beijing/11/2020
F247/Beijing/08/2014
F833/Beijing/09/2015
◆ MZ983592/60222008/Hannover/German/2021-HAdV-31-6-1
◆ OM372572/60346255/Hannover/German/2021-HAdV-31-6-2
Q1026/Beijing/09/2012
Q852/Beijing/05/2012
A320/Beijing/06/2022
Q904/Beijing/06/2012
CR6492/Beijing/05/2010
CR8581/Beijing/01/2013
Q553/Beijing/10/2011
CR6915/Beijing/01/2011
RV388/Beijing/02/2015
F2479/Beijing/05/2021
CR7121/Beijing/05/2011
CR7939/Beijing/03/2012
CR8146/Beijing/06/2012
CR8838/Beijing/05/2013
CR8888/Beijing/06/2013
CR9629/Beijing/05/2014
F1995/Beijing/11/2019
F734/Beijing/07/2015
Q603/Beijing/11/2011
CR7893/Beijing/02/2012
Q741/Beijing/03/2012
CR9445/Beijing/02/2014
F1397/Beijing/10/2016-Ad61
◆ JF964962/HAdV-A61 prototype/Japan/2004-HAdV-61
N825/Beijing/04/2017-Ad61
CR8939/Beijing/07/2013-Ad61
CR8612/Beijing/01/2013
CR8195/Beijing/07/2012
CR8204/Beijing/07/2012
◆ MW686774/Pt68 S1/UK/2019-HAdV-31-5-1
◆ MZ983596/60256333/Hannover/German/2021-HAdV-31-5-2
◆ MN901806/A61ONP01/ Toronto/Canada/2018-HAdV-61
◆ MG872324/HAdV-Tn2012/ Tunisia/2012-HAdV-31-4
◆ AM749299/HAdV-A31 prototype/UK/1962-HAdV-31-1a
◆ MZ983582/60086806/Hannover/German/2019HAdV-31-1b
◆ MZ983608/UL-E83731/Ulm/German/2014-HAdV-31-3
◆ MZ983607/M-23172/Munich/German/2016-HAdV-31-2c
◆ MZ983563/20334274/Hannover/German/2012-HAdV-31-2a
◆ MW686759/Pt6 S1/UK/2012-HAdV-31-2d
◆ MZ983567/20382908/Hannover/German/2014-HAdV-31-2b
P584/Beijing/03/2021-Ad61
◆ KX868289/GyK010/Sweden/1978-HAdV-12
◆ MN901805/A12ONP02/ Toronto/Canada/2018-HAdV-12
◆ GU191019/D.C./Washington D.C./USA/1954-HAdV-18
◆ KF360047/SAdV-ch1/China/2012-SAdV-ch1

Penton

F2230/Beijing/11/2020
RV388/Beijing/02/2015
F2096/Beijing/12/2019
F1797/Beijing/07/2018
CR8716/Beijing/03/2013
F1995/Beijing/11/2019
Q904/Beijing/06/2012
Q553/Beijing/10/2011
CR8581/Beijing/01/2013
◆ OM372572/60346255/Hannover/German/2021-HAdV-31-6-2
CR9629/Beijing/05/2014
A171/Beijing/12/2021
◆ MZ983592/60222008/Hannover/German/2021-HAdV-31-6-1
CR8838/Beijing/05/2013
CR7939/Beijing/03/2012
Q1026/Beijing/09/2012
F734/Beijing/07/2015
F1909/Beijing/07/2019
A320/Beijing/06/2022
F127/Beijing/06/2014
CR8593/Beijing/12/2012
CR8816/Beijing/05/2013
CR6915/Beijing/01/2011
CR9662/Beijing/05/2014
Q852/Beijing/05/2012
CR7121/Beijing/05/2011
CR8146/Beijing/06/2012
CR8888/Beijing/06/2013
F247/Beijing/08/2014
F833/Beijing/09/2015
F2479/Beijing/05/2021
CR6492/Beijing/05/2010
CR8612/Beijing/01/2013
Q603/Beijing/11/2011
Q741/Beijing/03/2012
CR7893/Beijing/02/2012
CR9445/Beijing/02/2014
CR8195/Beijing/07/2012
CR8204/Beijing/07/2012
◆ MW686774/Pt68 S1/UK/2019-HAdV-31-5-1
◆ MZ983596/60256333/Hannover/German/2021-HAdV-31-5-2
◆ MZ983608/UL-E83731/Ulm/German/2014-HAdV-31-3
◆ AM749299/HAdV-A31 prototype/UK/1962-HAdV-31-1a
◆ MG872324/HAdV-Tn2012/ Tunisia/2012-HAdV-31-4
◆ MZ983582/60086806/Hannover/German/2019HAdV-31-1b
◆ MZ983607/M-23172/Munich/German/2016-HAdV-31-2c
◆ MZ983563/20334274/Hannover/German/2012-HAdV-31-2a
◆ MW686759/Pt6 S1/UK/2012-HAdV-31-2d
◆ MZ983567/20382908/Hannover/German/2014-HAdV-31-2b
◆ GU191019/D.C./Washington D.C./USA/1954-HAdV-18
◆ KF360047/SAdV-ch1/China/2012-SAdV-ch1
◆ MN901806/A61ONP01/ Toronto/Canada/2018-HAdV-61
P584/Beijing/03/2021-Ad61
CR8939/Beijing/07/2013-Ad61
F1397/Beijing/10/2016-Ad61
◆ JF964962/HAdV-A61 prototype/Japan/2004-HAdV-61
N825/Beijing/04/2017-Ad61

Fiber

A171/Beijing/12/2021
CR8593/Beijing/12/2012
CR8716/Beijing/03/2013
CR8816/Beijing/05/2013
CR9662/Beijing/05/2014
F127/Beijing/06/2014
F1797/Beijing/07/2018
F1909/Beijing/07/2019
F2096/Beijing/12/2019
F2230/Beijing/11/2020
F247/Beijing/08/2014
F833/Beijing/09/2015
◆ MZ983592/60222008/Hannover/German/2021-HAdV-31-6-1
◆ OM372572/60346255/Hannover/German/2021-HAdV-31-6-2
Q1026/Beijing/09/2012
Q852/Beijing/05/2012
A320/Beijing/06/2022
Q904/Beijing/06/2012
CR6492/Beijing/05/2010
CR8581/Beijing/01/2013
Q553/Beijing/10/2011
CR6915/Beijing/01/2011
RV388/Beijing/02/2015
F2479/Beijing/05/2021
CR7121/Beijing/05/2011
CR7939/Beijing/03/2012
CR8146/Beijing/06/2012
CR8838/Beijing/05/2013
CR8888/Beijing/06/2013
CR9629/Beijing/05/2014
F1995/Beijing/11/2019
F734/Beijing/07/2015
Q603/Beijing/11/2011
CR7893/Beijing/02/2012
Q741/Beijing/03/2012
CR9445/Beijing/02/2014
F1397/Beijing/10/2016-Ad61
◆ JF964962/HAdV-A61 prototype/Japan/2004-HAdV-61
N825/Beijing/04/2017-Ad61
CR8939/Beijing/07/2013-Ad61
CR8612/Beijing/01/2013
CR8195/Beijing/07/2012
CR8204/Beijing/07/2012
◆ MW686774/Pt68 S1/UK/2019-HAdV-31-5-1
◆ MZ983596/60256333/Hannover/German/2021-HAdV-31-5-2
◆ MN901806/A61ONP01/ Toronto/Canada/2018-HAdV-61
◆ MG872324/HAdV-Tn2012/ Tunisia/2012-HAdV-31-4
◆ AM749299/HAdV-A31 prototype/UK/1962-HAdV-31-1a
◆ MZ983582/60086806/Hannover/German/2019HAdV-31-1b
◆ MZ983608/UL-E83731/Ulm/German/2014-HAdV-31-3
◆ MZ983607/M-23172/Munich/German/2016-HAdV-31-2c
◆ MZ983563/20334274/Hannover/German/2012-HAdV-31-2a
◆ MW686759/Pt6 S1/UK/2012-HAdV-31-2d
◆ MZ983567/20382908/Hannover/German/2014-HAdV-31-2b
P584/Beijing/03/2021-Ad61
◆ KX868289/GyK010/Sweden/1978-HAdV-12
◆ MN901805/A12ONP02/ Toronto/Canada/2018-HAdV-12
◆ GU191019/D.C./Washington D.C./USA/1954-HAdV-18
◆ KF360047/SAdV-ch1/China/2012-SAdV-ch1

0.02